

Shifting Towards the Highly Distributed Energy Ecosystem

Donát Dékány¹, László Vajta²

¹ Department of Control Engineering and Information Technology, Budapest University of Technology and Economics Budapest, Hungary

² Department of Control Engineering and Information Technology, Budapest University of Technology and Economics Budapest, Hungary

Abstract

Transforming a whole energy ecosystem from market mechanisms through the infrastructure upgrades and control operations to the behavior of the very last consumer takes a while. It has been already happening and we need to come up with solutions to face the coming challenges. The old, vertically integrated and centralized operation model is becoming a generally distributed network, where the consumers can become prosumers, energy flow is not one-directional, grid control operations are based on distributed optimization algorithms, and grid agents can effectively shape the characteristics of their consumption or generation. Different approaches are presented in this paper that could help the transformation of the energy ecosystem. Novel techniques are investigated to optimize grid control operations and market level cooperation as well. In the end, some suggestions for future work will be made.

1. Introduction

With the emerge of new technologies the conventional electricity generation systems have become obsolete, and the way electricity is generated, transmitted, and distributed is undergoing a major change.

Today, electricity markets are decentralized in many countries and allow consumers to choose the electricity supplier that best suits their preferences. In addition, generating units became more distributed as customer-side distributed generation (DG) appeared. Distributed energy resources (DER) has been gaining space and increasing complexity of the electricity grid system year by year. They include household photovoltaic and wind power, demand response (DR) and energy storage combined with innovative grid control solutions. Mentioned as an example, the most prominent in Europe, Belgium, currently has about 150 W of PV residential capacity per capita. The expected total capacity of residential photovoltaic installations in the European Union will reach 90 GW by 2021¹. By providing DERs in effective ways former traditional consumers will become active actors in the electricity market. These active actors are commonly referred to as DER agents which must have the following technical features to act as an agent.²:

- Distributed generation: Small-scale electricity generation at distribution voltage levels which can take the form of PV, wind power or other renewable sources.

- Load management: Agent can effectively control its load and follow control signals coming from the grid. It has the ability to schedule a certain load characteristic.

- Energy storage systems: refers to the device (e.g. batteries, either in electric-vehicles or stand alone, and other storage technologies) which possess the capability of electricity storage, import, and export back to the electricity network.

Figure 1: Network with distributed resources, smart loads and storages.

DER agents are managed by intelligent energy systems. However, electricity market nowadays offers compensation programs for DER agents to encourage the adoption of behind-the-meter renewable DG, the management of DERs for electricity system flexibility is very limited. The conventional electric system framework is not suitable to manage

the dynamic flow of electricity demands among increasing number of DER agents, and it does not take the advantage of the economic benefits.

The increasing adoption of DERs and smart grid technologies requires a new approach: a new concept of transactive energy which able to manage real-time dynamic electricity supply and demand in a reliable, sustainable system and considers a new market business model where agents can follow their own market strategies, interact with each other, and make deals on a free market². In such framework the decision making process of the individual agents are similar to the stock exchange mechanisms. This idea opens up another problem. Just like on the stock exchange, when automated agents follow different strategies, there is no guarantee that the system as a whole preserves its stability, and this can cause problems on physical control level of the grid.

2. 2. Recent electricity market and developments

For enhancing system coordination, suppliers and regulatory authorities are considering load flexibility – also known as demand response (DR) – typically in two different financial models, which can be price- or incentive based demand response programs. In the price based programs the customers have to shape their load curve to get the energy at a better price. Real time, critical peak, time of use and increasing block tariffs belong to this category. Incentive based model gives more space to the grid operator while the customer hand over control of its non-essential or flexible loads to get better energy prices. Such examples are the direct load control or the emergency demand response.

Wide adoption of DERs in the distribution grid depends on new technologies that enable higher efficiency, resilience, and flexibility to both technical and market operations.

2.1. Main technological challenges:

A vast amount of DERs can be considered as hidden assets that are invisible to operators because they are installed behind the meters. Load forecasting and power system operations become extremely difficult because DERs overshadow the real loads of that are located behind the same meter. Without significant developments, the current grid conditions do not allow the widespread of new DER agents that are not only consumers any more but prosumers with the ability of cooperation, real-time decision making, and management of their behavioral characteristics. These advances play an important role not only on distribution level, but on transmission level as well.

There are three areas where such developments would be essential:

- Planning which includes the physical infrastructure planning and the load planning and forecasting as well.

- Control and optimization techniques that ensures that ensures efficient reliable, and resilient operation.

- IT networks that interconnect the participating agents with an adequate connection at high security level.

Short term renewables, special loads, and dynamic pricing create a special environment, where planning and forecasting are the keys to avoid unnecessary infrastructure developments and identify the bottlenecks of the distribution grid where reinforcement is needed⁴. Transactive energy mechanisms can although handle the bottleneck problems with simple market-based tools, but the overall cost and welfare of the DER agents may not be optimal, so proper investment and grid expansion planning can help to lower overall operation costs. Unforeseen events can be seen in advance with proper big data analytics, as it helps to manage operational risks⁴.

In a vertically integrated system the DSO can perform a centralized control of the grid where the control signals are based on the measurements of the grid nodes. Operation is fairly predictable if there is no special load (e.g.: fast chargers) connected to the grid. It becomes challenging when a great number of special loads appear, then renewables are introduced (which has an unpredictable effect of the load curves), and finally prosumers appear who wants to make energy transactions with each other, and the grid operation has to be able to support these operations in order to maximize welfare of the DER agents. If the market operations are working among the agents, the DSOs will need to handle the reactive power control and face power flow limitations³. To implement transactive energy approaches DSOs should have the ability of dynamic pricing that shows the real cost of the energy in real time. (Resolution may vary, but in the long run it becomes real time). This approach is applicable for the loads and the generation as well. These problems need robust and adaptive optimization techniques that can be applicable in different distribution nodes.

The distribution grid is no longer just a problem to be solved in electricity, but also related to IT questions. The network of the future needs to manage the increasing amount of data produced by DER agents in real time which require a well-designed and implemented IT architecture. Today, IoT is a well-known concept - the requirements in the world of IoT are true here as well: the IT system should securely cover information sharing among DER agents, energy markets and transmission grids, real-time transactions in all points of the distribution grid as well as advanced monitoring⁵. It is essential that the system needs to be scalable and interconnected. Naturally, the interconnection and the real-time nature of the network mean vulnerability and increases the risk of attacks including intentional cyberattacks and issues in robust IT daily operation. Vulnerabilities might allow hackers to penetrate a network. Data of the transactions are confidential thus the appropriate security level must be implemented in order to maintain a secure energy market where every agent

participates on equal terms. The primary goal is prevention in all cases which might be ensured by identity and access management, threat protection and information protection. Here blockchain can be a potential solution to subserve multiparty transactions³⁰. In order to provide business continuity the network must be prepared to answer to issues quickly and in the worst case, for disaster recovery. This kind of cybersecurity threats are within the scope of the IoTAC project running in the Department of Control Engineering and Information Technology at BME. The goal of the project to create standards with industrial partners for different use cases of IoT security³¹.

2.2. Particular challenges on the field of control and optimization:

The complexities associated with grid integration of DERs can be addressed by different control mechanisms, in order to ensure the robust and stable operation of the network. Depending on the prioritization of the goals, different techniques and algorithms can be utilized. Most important goals are to ensure frequency and voltage level stability, but after these necessary conditions, a wide range of aspects can be emphasized. Such aspects are:

- maximize renewable energy intake into the grid

- local suppliers first
- best predictable suppliers first
- etc. . .

However the overall control mechanism should bring optimum operation for the grid, but due to the physical representation of the grid there will be obvious boundaries of the real-time control mechanism on the physical control level. On the top of the physical control layer another logical control layer can determine the energy transactions between the agents, in terms of power and price as well. These two operation levels has to operate as an integrated system where the logical layer can determine the setpoints for the physical layer thus creating an event-driven architecture to create control signals for the DER agents. On the logical (or business) layer different optimization methods can be adopted to effectively coordinate transactions among DER agents²³.

The distributed system where the grid control is based on the energy transactions of the agents, is called Transactive Energy System. Contrary to demand response management, that only focuses on the consumption part of the network, transactive systems can fully exploit the capabilities of the future smart grid systems by managing not only the demand but the DG and storage part of the system as well. Transactive energy systems use a transactive control refers to the utilization of a fully decentralized methodology based on local information and market data in order to reach the network balance and smoothing network fluctuations.

Control method in a transactive system can be carried

out in a centralized or decentralized way. In the centralized (or optimization-based) management methodology, a central controller engages with solving several mathematical problems mainly focused on an optimal solution for minimizing the operational costs of the entire grid. On the other hand, in a decentralized way (or transactive-control), the management unit does not have to solve complex optimization formulations. However, it provides optimal operational solutions by involving all network consumption and generation resources in a local energy auction bidding process.²⁴

Figure 2: Connected layers on the market and grid control level.

3. Researching methods to address challenges

Several methods are presented in the followings, that can be implemented in order to control transactive systems. These methods are usually combined for better results in real implementations.

3.1. Distributed Optimization

It has been always the basis of decision making problems to use optimization methods. Stochastic optimization, robust optimization, multi-objective optimization have been widely adopted for research on the wholesale market for market-clearance, and most of this research takes into consideration various types of uncertainties resulting from variable demand or renewable energy supply^{7, 8, 9}. However, since there are numerous decision variables at the distribution level associated with frequent monitoring activities and a large number of customers, especially given more and more small-sized local generation units, global optimization has become rarely implemented due to its increasing computational complexity. Consequently, the state-of-the-art strategy has begun to shift to distributed optimization with necessary decomposition, such as the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM), consensus-based algorithms, proximal message passing (PMP), and so on¹¹. Blockchain technology

has also attracted much attention due to the prevailing distributed optimization implementation in practice. It has been suggested as promising and suitable for such a decentralized decision-making process. Ref²⁸ describes the structure of peer-to-peer energy markets. The presented architecture ensures to adhere operational constraints without relying on central or hierarchical control. It proposes a blockchain-based solution and contracts to ensure transparency and clarity. It uses blockchain technology to make decentralized interactions between unreliable actors. Ref²⁹ propose a proportional-fairness control strategy in which the trustworthy implementation of the scheme is carried out through a custom-designed blockchain mechanism that maintains a distributed database trusted by all DERs.

3.2. Game Theory

In a highly distributed system, where agents act independently, game theory may be suitable for modeling the behavior of individual actors. Each agent seeks to maximize their own goals through interrelated interactions, but the game theory approach becomes more complicated if we assume that each branch can make more than just rational decisions.

Prospect theory is a theory of the psychology of choice, developed by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky, and applied in behavioral finance models. The theory describes how individuals decide between alternatives that involve risk and uncertainty in an asymmetric manner. Typically people tend to overweight low probabilities of bad outcomes and underweight high probabilities of favorable (average) opportunities. We can also say that prospect theory assumes subjective irrational decision-behavior unlike other traditional game theory methods. Therefore, it is worth incorporating prospect theory into the game theory approach of energy market behavior^{6, 13}. Highly complex systems pose a challenge to the game theory approach, as finding the equilibrium point is usually only possible with serious simplifications. This limits the applicability of the method.

A non-cooperative Stackelberg game is presented in ref¹⁰ between the DER agents and the grid controller. It explores how the cooperation among the agents and the grid can lead to a minimization of operation cost and in the meantime maximize the utilization. Ref¹² presents a design for an incentive mechanism using Nash bargaining theory to facilitate energy exchange with a fair compensation model. Each interconnected microgrid not only schedules its local power supply and demand, but also trades energy with other microgrids in a distribution network without centralized control.

3.3. Agent-Based Simulation

ABS has been available for more than 30 years to model different markets, which is also well applicable to the electricity market¹⁴. The strength of the method is really evident in the case of large-scale systems, where many interacting

actors are present. Each participant has its own characteristics in terms of its behavior, and interactions with other participants in the system determine their specific actions. In a simulation performed in this way, the complexity of the participants can range from quite simple to extremely complex, which can cause a very large number of state variations. With the incorporation of emerging learning algorithms and the availability of computational capacity, the method has become popular again in recent years. The method usually also endows each agent with a learning ability, which leads to the machine learning opportunities detailed below. Although the results of the ABS method are difficult to validate with real data, they are often used to test market processes before new rules are introduced.

3.4. Machine Learning

Among potential algorithmic possibilities, we obviously need to discuss machine learning methods which are essential components of any intelligent system nowadays. Machine learning - including supervised and unsupervised learning methods - is already applied in the electricity market most often for pattern recognition of consumption, demand response targeting¹⁵ and for pricing design. Reinforcement learning (RL) might have a decisive role in the energy business ecosystem by offering solutions to market transaction problems. Unlike other algorithms, in RL the agent interacts with its environment, performs actions and learns by a 'trial and error' method. Over other decision-making techniques, RL has the advantage of being suitable for an online environment where participation is voluntary and in addition, has sensitive data on consumption. However, the disadvantages of RL must be taken into account as most RL applications are highly dependent on Q-learning which offer low computational efficiency with ever-increasing datasets. The use of RL is appropriate in those scenarios of the energy market where the decision-making strategy needs to be optimized for common cases (e.g. high electricity demand during daytime) and infrequent states play a less significant role in optimization.

3.5. Combining methods

In reality, the approaches mentioned above are never implemented on their own. Nested together, they even correlate to form a multi-layered system. The ABS and machine learning methods discussed in the previous paragraph are often nested to endow each actor with a learning ability. Game theory methods can sometimes be interpreted as an optimization problem. The machine learning method can also be combined with optimization methods¹⁵.

Agents can only interact if they are neighbors, but a decentralized frequency control method can be carried out in a multi agent system that leverages average consensus algorithm in ref²¹. It shows that frequency stability can be ensured and agents can find consensus.

Ref²² examines the demand side behavior of an agent and constructs an adaptive method for decentralized demand side management. This method enables cooperation among the agents by shaping their load scheduling according to real-time energy prices.

A transactive control framework and realizations are presented in ref²⁵ focusing on the behavior of agents in transactive energy system. It analyses the centralized and the decentralized methods of control and presents game theoretical approaches of behavioral analysis.

Using an Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers a Dynamic Control and Optimization method of Distributed Energy Resources was proposed in ref²⁷. Model predictive control framework was set up to distribute optimization among DER agents. The algorithm is placed within this framework and enable them to dynamically change their behavior reflecting to real time external conditions. Embedded controllers model their own DERs as optimization problems at each time step. They use local objectives subject to individual constraints and forecasts. Simulations demonstrated the ability of this optimization framework to respond dynamically in real time and minimize total cost to the micro-grid while respecting and maintaining the functional requirements of all connected DERs.

Figure 3: Comparing methods regarding the computational complexity and the ability to easily handle agents as prosumers.

4. A European Outlook

Transformation of the energy ecosystem (which includes not only the electric energy) at European level is a hot topic nowadays in the EU. A new Strategy for Energy System integration is about to be accepted in the near future. It states that the energy system integration is the pathway towards

an effective, affordable and deep decarbonization of the European economy. It refers to the planning and operating of the energy system “as a whole”, across multiple energy carriers, infrastructures, and consumption sectors, by creating stronger links between them with the objective of delivering low-carbon, reliable and resource-efficient energy services, at the least possible cost for society. The strategy identifies six pillars of the upcoming transformation. Increasing energy efficiency across the whole energy system, accelerating electrification and renewables in the energy mix, promoting low-carbon or renewable fuels, making energy markets fit for decarbonization and distributed resources, integrating energy infrastructure and introducing innovative digital technologies³². The strategy proposes concrete policy and legislative measures at EU level to gradually shape a new integrated energy system. These recommendations are in line with the technologies presented in this paper, which shows that such technologies will play a key role in the future.

5. Smart Grid situation in Hungary

In terms of smart grid development, Central Europe is lagging far behind in Europe, and Hungary is performing poorly within the region. So far, only a few pilot projects have been implemented¹⁹.

Several elements of the set of conditions required for the use of smart grids or its elements have serious shortcomings. There is no legislation available regarding the development, deployment and operation of smart grids and the sharing of benefits and costs is unclear. Additional investments related to smart grids are not currently covered by the system usage fee. There is a low level of public awareness on relevant issues and the utilization of available but limited EU funds are also at a very low level. Smart grid development projects do not play a prominent role in smart city developments and if so, they include mostly renewable energy sources related developments.

There have been two attempts recently in Hungary to run a smart grid project:

Smart Synergy Project of DÉMÁSZ DSO based on Hungarian Law of Electricity to pilot smart metering in the country – both from supplier and from users’ side. The project was launched to examine the wholeness of smart metering rollout, also to obtain practical experiences on rolling out and operating the grid. The good practice was delivered and financed by Hungarian Distribution System Operator companies in 2012-2013. During the project 3000 electricity smart meters (500 of PLC and 2.500 of GPRS types) were installed in service area of DÉMÁSZ, South Great Plain Region of Hungary.

In the Central Smart Grid Pilot Project good practices initiated by the Hungarian Government strived for modernization of infrastructure for data collection, solving system regulation problems, integration of renewable energy sources

into the system, and piloting the country wide roll-out of smart metering. Installed electricity smart meters could form a smart grid on the concerned municipalities that took part in the pilot.

6. Conclusion

There is a continuous shift in minds how we look at our electric grid infrastructure. Due to the increasing integration of DERs in the distribution grid, we see the grid more like an multidirectional transaction network instead of a one-way supply chain. First applications like EV fast chargers (which make very unpleasant pikes in the load profile) and the unpredictable renewables like PVs or wind power (which transform the consumer into a prosumer when local surplus of energy occurs) showed that we need innovative technologies to ensure the reliability, resilience, and efficiency of transmission and distribution grids, and provide new services and functionalities to the grid agents.

This paper aimed to give an overview on the status and challenges of the new understanding of the distribution grid. Transactive energy concept goes forward in the energy transactions with deep concern on the local, distribution level perspective. Most of the current approaches are available as a model, lacking the real implementation in order to have a complete validation. Before such implementation, it is needed to develop and implement adequate simulation platforms and tools to analyze the different control techniques both on the market level and grid control level as well.

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